

Nitrogen Mustards. Part I. Reaction of Heterocyclic Amines with Ethylene Oxide

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Attempts to prepare nitrogen mustard intermediates from ethylene oxide and heterocyclic amines have not proved successful. The course of this reaction is discussed.

Some nitrogen mustards that have been synthesised from aromatic and aliphatic amines have shown sufficient antitumor activity and as such further work on this class of compounds has been considered desirable. The reaction of ethylene oxide with amines of aliphatic or aromatic class provides a good method for preparation of di-(β -hydroxyethyl)-amino derivatives which lead to the formation of nitrogen mustards by reaction with phosphorus oxychloride, thionyl chloride, etc. This method has been widely employed by Koss, Hanby and Rydon¹, Horne and Shriner², Headlee *et al.*³, Abrams *et al.*⁴, and Owen *et al.*⁵.

From literature, the reaction between ethylene oxide and heterocyclic amines appears to have received little attention. Gol'dfarb *et al.*⁷ reported that ethylene oxide appeared to react with 2-aminopyridine in dry acetone, but the yield was only in traces. They later obtained *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)-2-pyridonimine⁸ (b.p. 160-70°, m.p. 127-28°, hydrochloride m.p. 146-47.5°) in 20% yield from 2-aminopyridine and ethylene oxide and also *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)-2-pyridon-(2-hydroxyethyl)imine (m.p. 71-72°, hydrochloride m.p. 123-24°, picrate m.p. 119-20.5°) in a very poor yield. They had carried out the reaction in methanol. On the other hand, Yur'ev *et al.*⁹ reported that 1-(2-hydroxyethyl)- α -pyridonimine (m.p. 100°, b.p. 177-78°/7mm) was obtained by this reaction when heated at 60°. Subsequently Yur'ev *et al.*¹⁰ reported that 1,2-dihydro-1-(2-hydroxyethyl)-2-iminopyridine (m.p. 112°, b.p. 173-74°/11 mm) was obtained which on hydrolysis afforded 1-(2-hydroxyethyl)-2-(1*H*)-pyridone (b.p. 177-78°/7 mm, m.p. 100°). Gol'dfarb *et al.*⁸, however, obtained *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)-2-pyridone by hydrolysis of *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)-2-pyridon-(2-hydroxyethyl)imine. It is thus apparent that the results obtained by these two groups of Russian workers are not in harmony.

The reactions between ethylene oxide and 2-aminopyridine, 2-aminopyrimidine, and 3-aminoquinoline have been studied by us with a view to preparing di-(β -hydroxyethyl)-

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 182.
2. *Ibid.*, 1947, 513.
3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 2925.
4. *Ibid.*, 1933, 55, 1086.
5. *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1949, 68, 280.
6. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2800.
7. *Chem. Abs.*, 1952, 46, 8108.
8. *Ibid.*, 1956, 50, 3433.
9. *Ibid.*, 1955, 49, 7556.
10. *Ibid.*, 1956, 50, 4940.

amine derivatives (I). The reaction between ethylene oxide and 2-aminopyridine was carried out under drastic and mild conditions. In every case, the product was faint yellow needles, melting at 112-13° and affording picrates of m.p. 171-72°. That all these substances are identical is shown by the fact that the melting point is not depressed on admixture. Gol'dfarb⁸ has reported melting points of his substances (and also the picrate) which are quite different. Yur'ev *et al.*¹⁰ have, however, given a melting point which corresponds to our product.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

It is well known that 2- and 4-aminopyridines exist in the amine form, as pointed out by Goulden¹¹, Angyal *et al.*¹², and Katritzky *et al.*¹³. It is therefore tentatively suggested that the reaction between one mole each of ethylene oxide and 2-aminopyridine would lead to the formation of a compound which can be best represented by structure (II). This conclusion is further supported from a study of the UV spectra of 2-aminopyridine and compound (II), spectra of which are very similar both in aqueous and in hydrochloric acid solutions. There is only a slight bathochromic shift of the absorption maxima in the case of (II). There is thus a lack of evidence for the structure ascribed by Gol'dfarb⁸ and Yur'ev¹⁰. On similar grounds, compounds (III) and (IV) could represent the products of the reaction of ethylene oxide with 2-aminopyrimidine and 3-aminoquinoline respectively.

The reaction between ethylene oxide and 2-aminopyrimidine appears to proceed very smoothly at a low temperature, providing a fairly high yield of (III). On the other hand, 3-aminoquinoline afforded a small yield of (IV), although the reaction was carried out in cold and also with heating. Much of the 3-aminoquinoline was recovered unchanged after the reaction. In both cases, the analytical results show that only one mole of ethylene oxide reacts with one mole of the amine. Although it could be assumed that in the case of 2-aminopyridine and 2-aminopyrimidine some imino form is produced under the conditions of the reaction, this does not appear possible in the case of 3-aminoquinoline. It therefore appears that the course of the reaction follows a definite pattern. This pattern is probably the addition of one mole of ethylene oxide to the amino group and then subsequently other ethylene oxide molecules add on to the hydroxyl, giving rise to polymers. This may explain the formation of large amounts of materials which could not be distilled.

11. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 2939.

12. *Ibid.*, 1952, 1461, 2911.

13. *Ibid.*, 1950, 3674.

The expected compound, di-(β -hydroxyethyl)amine (I) could not be obtained in any case by any of the methods tried. So this reaction is not suitable for preparing nitrogen mustard intermediates of type (I) from heterocyclic amines. The reaction also failed to occur with 2-aminothiazole and 4-amino-2, 6-dimethylpyrimidine under mild conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-(β -Hydroxyethyl)aminopyridine (II): Method (a).—Ethylene oxide (5 ml) was cooled below 0° and added to 2-aminopyridine (2.75 g.), kept in a long tube; the tube was then sealed. This was heated at 110° for 11 hours, the tube was then opened, and the viscous dark mass was distilled under reduced pressure. The fraction boiling at 140-45°/10 mm was collected (2 g.). This was a dark viscous mass which deposited crystals (0.5 g.) when allowed to stand for 10 days in a refrigerator. The crystals were separated and washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and ethyl acetate. Finally it was recrystallised from the above solvents as faint yellow needles, m.p. 112-13°. (Found: N, 20.66. $C_7H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 20.30%). Picrate m.p. 171-72°. (Found: N, 19.72. $C_{13}H_{13}O_8N_5$ requires N, 19.08%). λ_{max} 232, 305 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 5989, 4961); free base in water: λ_{max} 232, 304 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 6437, 5154) in 10% hydrochloric acid solution.

Method (b).—Ethylene oxide and 2-aminopyridine in the same proportion as above were heated in a sealed tube at 50-60° for 3 hours. The tube was then allowed to stand for two months when the dark viscous mass solidified. This was taken out and recrystallised from ethyl acetate and petroleum ether (yield 20%) in yellowish needles, m.p. 112-13°; picrate m.p. 171-72°.

Method (c).—Ethylene oxide (4 ml) was added to 2-aminopyridine (2.35 g.), dissolved in ice-cooled methanol (15 ml). The mixture was kept in a refrigerator for two weeks and then distilled under reduced pressure after removing the solvents. The fraction boiling at 140-50°/3 mm was collected as a thick yellow liquid (0.5 g.) which later solidified. It was crystallised from petroleum ether and ethyl acetate in yellowish needles, m.p. 112-13°; picrate m.p. 171-72°.

2-(β -Hydroxyethyl)aminopyrimidine (III).—Ethylene oxide (14.08 g., 80% of theoretical) was dissolved in ice-cold water (16 ml) and added dropwise to an ice-cold solution of 2-aminopyrimidine (19 g.) in water (100 ml) with vigorous stirring. In order to prevent the escape of ethylene oxide, a spiral condenser was attached to the reaction flask through which ice water was circulated. The stirring was continued for half an hour after the addition of ethylene oxide was complete. The solution was then allowed to stand overnight at 30° and then water removed at a reduced pressure. The residue was distilled in vacuum. The fraction boiling at 159-60°/10 mm was collected. This was a thick yellowish liquid which solidified to a white mass (12 g., 36%). This was repeatedly crystallised from benzene (charcoal) as white silky needles, m.p. 78-79.5°. (Found: N, 30.78. $C_6H_8ON_2$ requires N, 30.21%) Picrate m.p. 140-42°. (Found: N, 23.69. $C_{12}H_{12}O_8N_6$ requires N, 22.82%). λ_{max} 235, 300 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 17750, 3475), free base in water.

*All melting points are uncorrected.

3-(*β*-Hydroxyethyl)aminoquinoline (IV): *Method (a)*.—Ethylene oxide (8 ml, 80% of theoretical) was dissolved in water (8 ml) and cooled in an ice-salt bath. This was slowly added to a solution of 3-aminoquinoline (14.4 g., 0.1 *M*) in water (50 ml), and cooled in the ice-salt bath with stirring. The reaction flask was provided with a spiral condenser to prevent the escape of ethylene oxide. The mixture was stirred for 1/2 hr. After the addition was complete and allowed to stand for 24 hours at room temperature. Water was then removed under reduced pressure from the mixture and a thick blood-red liquid was obtained. This was distilled in vacuum and the fraction boiling at 190-95°/1.2 mm was collected as a thick, deep brown liquid (2 g.). It gave a *picrate*, m.p. 187-88°. (Found: N, 16.65. C₁₇H₁₃O₈N₃ requires N, 16.78%).

Method (b).—Ethylene oxide (8 ml, 80% of theoretical) was passed as a gas in a thoroughly stirred solution of 3-aminoquinoline (14.4 g., 0.1 *M*) in water (85 ml) and the mixture was heated at 80°. The reaction completed in about an hour and the stirring was continued for half an hour more. The solution was allowed to stand overnight in a refrigerator. Water was removed under reduced pressure and the thick brown residue distilled in vacuum; the fraction boiling at 212-15°/1.8 mm was collected as a thick, orange yellow liquid (2 g.) which deposited crystals on standing for some days in a refrigerator. This was recrystallised from benzene (bone charcoal) in yellowish needles, m.p. 125-27°. (Found: N, 15.21. C₁₇H₁₃O₈N₃ requires N, 14.89%). *Picrate* m.p. 187-188°. (Found: N, 16.65. C₁₇H₁₃O₈N₃ requires N, 16.78%). λ_{max} 268,400 mμ (ε, 19458, 2688) in dilute hydrochloric acid solution.

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